

METHODS OF FORMATION OF CUSTOMS TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: Customs, like any other science, is associated with terminology. Currently, terminology as a special field of knowledge is attracting more and more attention, which is explained by the international nature of modern scientific knowledge, due to the process of integration and, as a result, the desire to unify terms as a way to overcome language barriers in various areas of socio-economic activity. This article is devoted to the study of tax-customs terminology.

Key words: terminology, tax-customs, linguistics, structural semantics.

All languages of the world are developing in one way or another, this is especially noticeable in the lexical sphere, because it is in it that significant changes are taking place associated with the emergence of a large number of new words. Their formation can be explained by the fact that the language is influenced by various factors. So, for example, in the customs business, the formation of words is due to the influence of the human factor, internal processes and patterns of the sphere itself, as well as economics, foreign trade, politics, finance, jurisprudence, etc.

It is in the customs business that constant updates in legislation take place, which depend on the improvement and harmonization of foreign trade activities, the rapid development of international relations. Customs, like any other science, is associated with terminology. Currently, terminology as a special field of knowledge is attracting more and more attention, which is explained by the international nature of modern scientific knowledge, due to the process of integration and, as a result, the desire to unify terms as a way to overcome language barriers in various areas of socio-economic activity.

Customs vocabulary reflects the current level of development of the English language, which suggests that it reflects the processes characteristic of word formation at the moment.

The most relevant in customs, as in any other professional field, is English. In the English-language customs vocabulary, new concepts are formed due to a multicomponent combination of terminological nature. There are combinations such as:

Affixation - the formation of words by attaching various word-building affixes to the root or stem of a word.

- spelling change - control - controller;
- semantic allow - allowance;
- change of part of speech.

Such changes occur due to suffixation. Several groups of suffixes have been identified in the customs vocabulary:

- verbalizing: *-ate (to motivate), -ize, -ise (to specialize), -en (to threaten), -ify (to notify)*;
- adverbializing: *-ly (permanently), -wards (sideways)*;
- adjectives: *-able (transportable), -ent, -ant (divergent), -ing (missing), -al (personal), -ous (dangerous), -ful (powerful), -ed (permitted)*;

- substantiating: *-er, -or (border, consignor), -ent, -ant (complicant), -ee (guarantee), -age (message), -ing (networking), -ness (acidness), -ance, -ence (clearance), -ion, -ation, -ition (declaration, examination), -ate (directorship), -ment (consignment, shipment), -ism (officialism), -ure (procedure).*

- Composition - the formation of new words by adding the bases of two words: *work + flow = workflow (document flow control)*

- Reduction

The least common, but no less interesting of the combination methods is reduction. Abbreviation can be called the best option for creating a short term.

Abbreviations of customs terminology include such groups as:

1. Initial abbreviations

They are considered the most numerous of the groups. Initial abbreviations are a combination of the initial letters of the words of the original terminological combination, or elements of compound words:

TMS (transportation management systems); IPEA (International Preliminary Examination Authority).

The initial abbreviation can be formatted with dots:

C.C.E.F. (Customs Centralized Examination Facility) - the central point of customs inspection

Such abbreviations do not look like words, but gradually their use in writing leads to skipping points, so the abbreviation begins to be pronounced as a combination of sounds and becomes acronyms.

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